

Interpretation idea of dynamical topological phase in concept of ordinal

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Abstract

Recent study suggests dynamical topological phase could be derived into additional dimension of time. By adding interpretation of this phenomenon with a topological interaction within simplified model, possibility of approaching many-timeline in real world could be suggested.

1 Introduction

Current understanding of physics in standard model invites us to the reality of possible multiverse. In extent of actualizing this, many-timeline perspective could be possible in view of dynamical topological phase, which has been introduced in a recent study [1].

2 Many Timeline by Topological Phase

Difference in topological phase and common spin-like concept in a single particle is that it constitutes phase by organizing in CPT. As a very-simplified explanation in difference of EDSPT and FSPT is that of existence of T symmetry and its violation.

As FSPT in relation used their logic gates in only by a single step, not in a consideration of ordinal order. But as for EDSPT, they used Fibonacci drive to ensure relation among the particles to be related in a series of quantum gates.

This makes dynamical topological order in suggestion of many timeline. Continuing discussion in simulating universe [2], every spin in perturbation could position an angle like in given time t :

$$\begin{aligned}\sin \theta \sum_t^{\forall t} \frac{CR_n}{r} - \cos \left(\theta - \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \sum_t^{\forall t} SR_m \cdot r &\approx 0 \\ \sin \theta \sum_t^{\forall t} \frac{SR_n}{r} - \cos \left(\theta - \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \sum_t^{\forall t} CR_m \cdot r &\approx 0\end{aligned}$$

So that by making a topological LIOM(local integrals of motion) in a perturbed time sequence the temporal topology in given integrated phase could be stateful(e.g. could be in continuous(predictable) distribution of Gaussian). So that it acts like a train passing a equal size of tunnel. Although the full size and shape of train is standardized, but observer outside the tunnel could see the partial result until a train fully passes by it.

In uniform of particle in P and within given period,
Let $f : X \rightarrow Y, f \in C(X, Y)$ and $g : X \rightarrow Y, g \in C(X, Y)$, Constant $C \in \mathbf{C}$
 $Var(\sin \theta_t - \sin \theta_{t-1}) \approx f, \sum P \approx C \Rightarrow Var(r) \sim g$

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3 New Possibility of Phase in Strong Relation

Then how can this relation could be more to be utilized? For a suggestion in quantum bit, it could be utilized in elongation of continuous parallel calculation. While many-body quantum in a quantum gate acts more stabilized, in other perspective, it narrow a gap in conditioning of quantum gate which like suggested in the paper [1]. This makes more room for more parallel execution of quantum gates like, other charge or parity symmetry and its violation related quasi-particle.

So, to gain more strong relation in this ‘dynamical topological’ type bit, regulation as a spin is important but also the topology that energy level creates matter.

4 Interpretation of Many Timeline

With the result, new possibility of many timeline could be suggested. As in preceding example of a train, if regulation of spin is limited in moment of observation, spin of other timelines that could take diversifies. This needs more to be studied.

5 Conclusion

1. Recent study has shown possibility of many timeline in a spin, dynamical topological state possibly be a way of diversification in dimensionality of time.
2. Strong relation as a new possibility of phase could possibly be related with energy level of integrated topology.
3. Many timeline in many-body particle may be suggested in a sense of approaching observation in different ways.

References

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